

Table 2. Height, duration, and fertility of F₁s test crops involving 8 CMS lines.* CRS, Masodha, Faizabad, UP, India, 1987-90 WS.

Variety	Height	Duration	1987-88		1988-89		1989-90			
			V20 A	IR46830 A	IR54752 A	ES18 A	Madhu A	Pragathi A	Pushpa A	Mangla A
Narendra 1	Dwarf	Early	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Narendra 2	Dwarf	Early	PR	PR	PR	—	PR	PM	—	PM
Narendra 80	Tall	Early	PR	PM	PR	—	PM	—	PM	PM
Narendra 1.18	Dwarf	Early	R	PR	R	PR	PR	—	PM	PM
IR8	Dwarf	Medium	PM	—	PR	PM	PM	—	PM	—
IR24	Dwarf	Medium	R	R	PR	PM	PM	—	PM	—
Saket 1	Tall	Early	PR	PR	R	—	PM	—	PM	PM
Saket 3	Dwarf	Early	—	PM	R	—	PR	PM	PM	PM
Saket 4	Dwarf	Early	R	PR	R	PM	PM	—	PM	PM
Sarjoo 52	Dwarf	Medium	PR	PR	R	PM	PM	—	PM	—
Sattari	Dwarf	Early	PM	—	—	PM	—	—	—	PM
Manhar	Dwarf	Medium	PM	PM	—	PM	PM	PM	—	PM
Sita	Dwarf	Medium	—	PM	—	PM	PR	—	—	—
Madhuri	Dwarf	Early	PM	PM	PR	PM	—	PM	PM	PM
Jaya	Dwarf	Medium	—	PM	—	PM	—	PM	PM	—
Satha 34-36	Tall	Early	R	—	R	PM	—	PM	PM	—
China 4	Tall	Early	PR	PR	PM	PM	—	—	—	—
Boro Gazipur	Tall	Early	—	PM	—	PM	PM	—	—	—
Boro Mirzapur	Tall	Early	—	PM	PM	PM	PM	—	—	PM
Jhona 349	Tall	Early	—	—	PM	—	PM	—	—	—
Cauvery	Dwarf	Early	PM	PR	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Govind	Dwarf	Early	—	PR	PR	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM
Mahsuri	Tall	Late	—	PR	PM	—	PR	—	PM	PM
T100	Tall	Late	PR	—	PR	—	PR	—	—	—
N22	Tall	Early	PM	PR	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM

*R = restorer, PR = partial restorer, PM = partial maintainer.

(WS). Based on spikelet fertility of F₁s, the rice varieties were categorized as effective restorers (80-100% spikelet fertility), partial restorers (21-79% spikelet fertility), partial maintainers (2-20% spikelet fertility), and maintainers (0-1% spikelet fertility).

Narendra 118, Saket 4, and Satha 34-36 were identified as restorers for V20 A and IR54752 A, and IR24 for IR46830 A (Table 2). No varieties were identified as restorers for ES18 A, Madhu A, Pragathi A, Pushpa A, and Mangla A, and no varieties were identi-

fied as effective maintainers for any CMS lines in this study. Results indicate that CMS source wild abortive was genetically diverse from MS577. ■

Genotypic differences in embryogenic callus formation and plant regeneration in indica rice

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Fifteen indica varieties were used for determining response to embryogenic callus induction and plant regeneration (see table). Embryos were separated from mature, dehusked seeds that had been soaked in sterile distilled water for 24 h at 28 °C. Embryos were cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with 3% sucrose and 0.8% agar adjusted

to pH 5.8 and supplemented with 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter.

We observed variations in culture responses among genotypes. Calli formed at the scutellar surface after 1 wk of culture. Himalaya 1 did not form any calli. Genotypes formed either embryogenic or nonembryogenic calli or both types. Embryogenic calli were compact, nodular, loosely globular, shiny, dry in appearance, and yellow to cream in color. Nonembryogenic calli were friable in appearance, white to brown in color, and occasionally developed roots.

On the basis of embryogenic callus formation, Chambal, CH1039, HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B, Himdhan,

HPU5101, HPU2202, and IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2 were selected for regeneration (see table). Four-week-old calli of these genotypes were maintained on MS medium supplemented with 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter. For plant regeneration, calli (about 1.15 g from each callus) from the second subculture were plated onto MS medium supplemented with three levels of BAP (0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/liter) and NAA (0.05, 0.1, and 0.5 mg/liter) in various combinations.

We observed that calli did not regenerate at 0.5 mg BAP/liter and 0.05 mg NAA/liter. At the higher level BAP and NAA combination, a high frequency of regeneration was observed in Chambal, CH1039, and Himdhan

Embryogenic and nonembryogenic callus induction and plant regeneration from indica rice genotypes.

Genotype	Callus type ^a	Callus growth ^b	Calli plated for regeneration (no.)	Plants regenerated ^c (no.)	
				Green	Albino
Chambal	E	+++ (50)	40	219	181
CH1039	E	+++ (50)	48	588	-
CH988	NE	++ (25)	-	-	-
HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B	E	+ (12)	48	72	-
HPU2216	NE	++ (37)	-	-	-
HPU5101	E	++ (17)	52	130	-
HPU2202	E	+++ (58)	32	72	-
Himalaya 1	NR	-	-	-	-
Himalaya 741	NE	+ (25)	-	-	-
Himdhan	E	+++ (42)	44	297	-
IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2	E	++ (8)	32	-	-
IR36	NE	+ (25)	-	-	-
K39	NE	+ (37)	-	-	-
Kaladhan	NE	+++ (75)	-	-	-
R575	NE	++ (8)	-	-	-

^aCallus induction medium = MS + 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter. E = embryogenic callus, NE = nonembryogenic callus, NR = no response. ^b+ = poor, ++ = moderate, +++ = good to excellent, - = not attempted. Values in parentheses indicate the percentage of response among replicates. ^cPlant regeneration medium = MS + 1.0 mg BAP/liter and 0.1 mg NAA/liter.

(see table). HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B, HPU2202, and HPU5101 regenerated into green plantlets but at a lower frequency. IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2 did not regenerate. Chambal, CH1039, and Himdhan were considered more responsive than the others to callus formation and plant regeneration. Chambal had a high frequency of albino plants.

The results indicate that embryogenic callus formation and plant regeneration ability vary among indica rice genotypes. ■

Effect of interaction between genotype and culture medium on callus induction and plant regeneration of anther culture of Vietnamese indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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We evaluated the response of 12 Vietnamese indica rice genotypes (including F₁ promising lines, and varieties) to anther culture using several callus induction media (CIM) and plant regeneration media (PRM). Anther culture can complement the rice breeding program in Vietnam by offering the advantage of rapid achievement of homozygosity.

Anthers with microspores at the mid-uninucleate to early binucleate stage of development were plated on CIM G1, Fj, and L8 (Table 1) at a density of 15 anthers/ml of medium. The plated anthers were incubated in the dark at 25±1°C. Callus induction percentage was recorded 2 mo after culture and calculated as number of callus-producing anthers relative to total anthers plated. We transferred calli of 1-2 mm diameter to

Table 1. Constituents of callus induction media.

Constituent	Medium (mg/liter)		
	G1	Fj	L8
KNO ₃	2830	3150	3000
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	463	220	-
KH ₂ PO ₄	170	540	540
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	185	185	185
CaCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O	440	150	150
MnSO ₄ · 4H ₂ O	4.4	22.3	22.3
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.5	10.0	10.0
H ₃ BO ₃	6.2	6.0	6.0
KI	0.83	1.0	1.0
CuSO ₄ · 5H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
CoCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
NaMoO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
Na ₂ EDTA	37.25	37.25	37.25
FeSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	27.85	27.85	27.85
Glycine	2.0	2.0	-
Thiamine-HCl	2.5	2.0	2.5
Pyridoxine-HCl	2.5	2.0	5.0
Nicotinic acid	2.5	2.0	3.0
Lactalbumin	-	-	500.0
Casein hydrolysate	500.00	500.0	-
Inositol	100.0	100.0	100.0
2,4-D	2.0	0.5	0.5
Naphthalene acetic acid	2.5	2.5	2.0
Sucrose	40000	40000	40000
Agar	8000	8000	8000
pH	5.8	5.8	5.8